

ANDALUS (BERANDA PEMUDA MUSLIM) AS AN ANDROID APPLICATION BASED LEARNING MEDIA ON STUDY AL-QUR'AN FOR MILLENNIAL GENERATION

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Abstract

Islam guarantees life for every adherent in the world and in the hereafter and Islam has a very essential joint of the Qur'an. Samsul Nizar (2002) says Islamic education is a series of systematic, planned and comprehensive process in an effort to transfer the values to the students, develop the potential of the students, so that students are able to carry out their duties on earth as best as possible all dimensions of life. The millennial issue of Muslims is now very worrisome because they started away with their Qur'an, do not want to learn Arabic which is the language to understand the Qur'an and more closely with its gadgets. Arsyad (2017) says the visual media can attract and direct people's attention to concentrate on the content of an information, in which case the visual source can inspire one's emotions and attitudes so as to speed up the process of understanding and remembering messages. Based on that statement, the right solution in helping millennials in the process of understanding the Qur'an is by developing a translation application of the Qur'anic Tafsir Ibnu Katsir with an audio and visual display called ANDALUS. ANDALUS is a medium of information, and an android based communication to welcome the industrial revolution 4.0 to the millennium to get closer to the Qur'an. This research uses research and development method. The results of this study show a high appreciation because the millennials consider the translation of the Qur'an more easily understood and easy to remember. In addition, this application also contains all the verses of the Qur'an so that the millennial more understand the contents of the Qur'an universally.

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1. Introduction

Islamic education guarantees life for every adherent in the world and hereafter. Islamic education has very essential joints, namely the Qur'an and Sunnah. It contains basic teachings (basic principles) concerning all aspects of human life, which then can be developed according to the reason of each nation, whenever the time, and wherever it is, Islam is always present functionally solving humanitarian problems, because everything is contained in it [1]. Samsul Nizar (2002) writes in his book, Islamic education is a series of systematic, planned and comprehensive processes in an effort to transfer values to students, developing the potential that exists in students, so that students are able to carry out their duties on the earth as well as in all dimensions of life. The problem of the current Muslim millennial is very worrying because they start far away with the Qur'an, do not want to learn Arabic which is a language to understand Al-Quran and get closer to the gadget. The rapid growth of the internet is one of the reasons for this.

The Internet has touched and changed almost the human life side, reached 3 million Internet users in the world in 2016 [2]. Predictions from Google Executive Chairman Eric Schmidt mention that by 2020 all the world's populations are connected to the Internet. The International

Telecommunication Union (ITU) reports that 80% of teenagers (15-24) in 104 countries are online using Mobile Smartphones [3]. The number of Smartphone usage in Quarter 3rd 2016 worldwide has touched 7.5 billion, specifically for comparison market shares operating system (OS) is controlled by Android 65%, and the rest by IOS, Windows Phone, and Blackberry [4]. Smartphones in Indonesia now reach about 25% of the total population or about 90 million people and increase 6 million per year [5]. Indonesia is going digital with 261 million population around 13,700 islands, 33 provinces, over 500 districts with roughly 58 million learners, 3 million teachers, and 302,097 schools [6].

In general, the challenge of education in Indonesia is a high priority to increase learners' interest in learning, improving teacher quality, increasing efficiency, and effectiveness of media based learning [7]. Khaeruddin Said (2018) have published a research Development of Media-Based Learning using Android Mobile Learning that the conclusion of his paper can be taken based on data of research result and discussion of android application development as learning media is very decent. The delivery of information and learning materials to the learner's from teachers is more interactive, involving more contact, communication and collaboration with people easily, inexpensively and accessibility anywhere and anytime. Comparison with other digital learning media such as using desktop-based/notebook-based multimedia is quite troublesome, expensive and immobile for the learner [8].

Arsyad said visual media can attract and direct people's attention to concentrate on the contents of an information. In this case visual sources can arouse a person's emotions and attitudes so that they can speed up the process of understanding and remembering messages. According to the Education and Communication Technology Association in America, media are all forms and channels that people use to send messages or information. The National Education Association has a different understanding of media, they define media as forms of both printed and audiovisual communication and equipment. The media can be used to send messages from the sender to the recipient so that it can stimulate students' thoughts, feelings, attention and interests in such a way that the learning process occurs [9].

Mobile Learning very helpful for students in understanding learning. Muhammad Hassan Massaty (2017) make an application call Sekar Indonesia. Sekar Indonesia had been tested its performance and its feasibility. From the performance test was known all function worked properly for each smarthphone with different specification. The result of feasibility test of Sekar Indonesia learning media is done by material experts, media experts and users. The average of the overall aspects of the feasibility of materials experts, media experts and users is 86.1%, 92.85% and 98%. From these results indicate that the application of Sekar Indonesia is very appropriate to serve as a companion learning media for students [10].

We have shown how an agent can extract information from an audio-visual content following a theoretical formulation based on the Channel Theory. After showing it, we have established a possible method of representation of all the informative values that an agent can obtain from a content using a matrix formed by the channels the agent is able to establish on the content. Finally, we have exposed how this representation allows us to illustrate the evolution of informative items through the evolution of audio-visual content. The next objective of this research is to assess how the variations of the information matrix can allow the obtaining by the agent of new classifications and channels that go beyond the objects represented in the content, and also can allow an approach to the understanding of the semantic and syntactic levels of content by the agent [11].

Receiving information from different senses is highly advantageous since events become more salient which in turn enables quicker and more adequate responses to crossmodal compared to unimodal stimuli [12]. Despite a huge body of research the question of how the brain combines information from the different senses into a coherent percept is still not fully understood. It has been suggested that so-called supramodal features, that is, features which are redundantly coded

by multiple sensory systems, are used to judge whether or not inputs from different modalities originate from the same source. Examples of supramodal features are time, space, number and meaning⁴: the higher the overlap of inputs from different sensory modalities with regard to supramodal features, the more likely the brain will treat these inputs as coming from the same source. For example, a bouncing ball makes a sound each time the ball hits the ground and both sound and visual motion appear at the same location. Hence it is likely to perceive one object producing both types of sensory input [13].

Roger Bergh (2015) The information base solution will support teachers, instructors, Small and Medium Sized Enterprises with training methods promoting pedagogical use of audio and video technology into instructional processes. The new training principles aim to facilitate this integration through the dissemination of information on good practices and the fostering of a community of peers for the sharing of information and experiences, both technical and pedagogical. The new audio-visual information base services, to be completed in the fall of 2007, offer the European educational society model recommendations for pedagogical use, as well as adaptation and effective integration of audio-visual communication and collaboration services for transfer of training, competence and knowledge to Small and Medium Sized Enterprises (SME). The services aim at the creation and fostering of a community within distance education for the sharing of information related to the integration of audio and video technology within pedagogical methodologies [14].

M. Alqahtani and A. Fayyumi (2015) Technology in the educational process is not new and mobile learning applications are becoming more pervasive. Therefore, it is very necessary to understand their impact if being used in learning options. Nowadays, great efforts are being made to develop speech recognition applications for mobile devices. It helps the user to interact with the device as if he was speaking to another person. Arabic speech recognition has its challenging characteristics and many researchers have performed studies regarding them. One of them is how to recognize verbal Quran verses. This study focuses on developing the Say Quran Android application and then studying the attitudes of students toward this application. This work can be improved and more work can be done to add modifications and additional features. The current version of the software supports only a few languages but more languages can be added in the future work. More importantly, an in-depth study of the impact of such an application on students' learning should be conducted [15].

Yapeng Tian (2018) makes research In this work, we study a suit of five research questions in the context of three audio-visual event localization tasks. We propose both baselines and novel algorithms to address each of the three tasks. Our systematic study also supports our findings: modeling jointly over auditory and visual modalities outperforms independent modeling, audio-visual event localization in a noisy condition is still tractable, the audio-guided visual attention is able to capture semantic regions of sound sources and can even distinguish audio-visual unrelated videos, temporal alignments are important for audio-visual feature fusion, the proposed dual residual network is capable of audio-visual fusion, and strong correlations existing between the two modalities enable cross-modality localization [16].

So, the right solution to help millennials in the process of getting closer to the Koran is by developing an Al-Quran translation media with audio and visual appearance. A concrete solution that can be applied is to develop an application called ANDALUS (Beranda Pemuda Muslim). ANDALUS is an Android-based learning, information and communication media to welcome the industrial revolution 4.0 to the millennials to get closer to the Qur'an.

2. Objectives

The purpose of this research is to produce Android-based learning media, information, and communication devices in the form of Al-Quran translation media with audio and visual display.

The benefit of making this media is to help Muslim youth be able to carry out their duties on the earth as well as possible in all dimensions of life.

3. Methodology

3.1. Place and Time of Research

This study was conducted for two months from July to August 2018 which focused on the design of the media at the Secretariat of the Young Research Group of the Jakarta State University.

3.2. Research Stages

The research begins with conducting a needs analysis using user analysis questionnaire techniques. The research process continued on the feasibility test by the expert team in terms of material and media using interview techniques. The resulting product was tested to users in small groups using a questionnaire.

3.3. Research Methods

The research method used in the study uses the Research and Development method. According to Sugiyono, Method of Research and Development or research development is a research method used to produce certain products, and test the effectiveness of these products. The development method adapts from the ADDIE development model developed by Dick and Carry to design learning media. The development model consists of five stages which include analysis (analysis), design (design), development (implementation), and implementation (evaluation).

4. Result and Discussion

4.1. Product Development Results

4.1.1. Product Needs Analysis

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The results of the needs analysis showed that 58.1% of respondents did not understand what he was reading from the Koran, 74.4% of respondents tried to read the translations of the Koran to understand the content of the Koran and the rest varied, some by listening to studies and some by asking. In addition, 90.7% said they all had the Al-Quran application on their smartphones. And unfortunately they only read the translation without knowing the interpretation that is more or less possible different from the meaning of the verse. Also the data shows that they feel comfortable every day with a short video display that contains audio at the same time as visual, they feel more focused when seeing it which is around 89.5%. So from that analysis we direct if the Qur'anic interpretation application is made with their audio visual form, they answer 82.6% agree and like it.

4.1.2. Media Making Design

The media manufacturing stage is the realization stage of the flowchart design, at this stage learning media is created using Android Studio, Corel Draw, and Wondershare Filmora software.

Steps for Making an Application using Corel Draw: The first step is to open the Corel Draw worksheet for the new clinics in the window and select a custom paper worksheet with a full 1000 pt x 1000 pt.

The appearance made guided by the interpretation of Ibn Katsir which is the most widely known book of interpretation. Then a visual appearance is made using corel draw with a phrase quotation according to the interpretation of Ibn Katsir. After the display is made, the audio is added with voice dubbing and combined using the Wondershare Filmora application. Lastly, the phrase quotations quran are uploaded to the android application according to the flowchart in Figure 1.

After the content is ready, then coding is done on the Android application by using the Android Studio application by referring to the flowchart that has been created. Display of Android studio worksheets as shown in Figure 2.

Figure 1. Application flowchart to be created

Figure 2. Display Android studio work to create applications

Android apps that have been filled with Quran content can be accessed using a smartphone with a minimum of Android 5.0 specifications.

4.1.3. Product Development

The media manufacturing stage is the realization stage of the flowchart design, at this stage learning media is created using Android Studio, Corel Draw, and Wondershare Filmora software.

Figure 1. Picture of the Andalus Application

Figure 2. Selected Mail Menu Options

Figure 3. Surat View

4.2. Research result

In this study, the researcher carried out the stages, namely taking data to media experts and material experts using Likert scale questionnaires and interviews as well as questionnaires to usability tests for users in small groups.

4.2.1. Media Expert Validation Results

Based on the results of interviews obtained from media experts, His name is Med Irzal, M.Kom lecturers of the UNJ Computer Science study program, stated that the appearance of colors, images and audio is good enough. However, the appearance of the application is like a normal website. In addition, structure and navigation are not consistent and difficult to understand. So, the application must be repaired again.

4.2.2. Expert Validation Results Material

After making improvements to it, the research application validated the material experts, her name is Dian Nurohmah alumni of the Sukoharjo Al-Uthuwah Islamic Boarding School and also the teaching staff at the As As Sakinah Youth Study Salman Al - Farisi Rawamangun Mosque. The result of the interview that the content of the application is good. Audio visuals are also quite supportive in the process of understanding the Qur'anic interpretation. However, foreign words that are difficult to understand by ordinary people should be eliminated. In order not to cause mistreatment. after validation is carried out immediately revised according to the direction of experts. after the revision was done, the researcher conducted a usability test.

4.2.3. Usability Test Results

Jako Nielsen stated that for usability test, it was enough with only 5 respondents, because in testing the users who were the focus was the site's functionality to see which design elements were easy and which were difficult to use. Evaluating the quality of design elements does not depend on how many people use the application. Therefore, the researcher decided to spread the questionnaire to only 5 respondents.

The measurement technique used is using a Likert scale. For the purposes of quantitative analysis, answers are given a predetermined score of one, two, three, four and five.

Table 1. The Likert Scale

NO	Kategori	Skor
1	Very good	5
2	Good	4
3	Enough	3
4	Less	2
5	Very Less	1

The percentage of eligibility is calculated using the formula:

$$\% = \frac{\text{Number of Answer Scores}}{\text{The Maximum Total Score of Each Indicator}} \times 100\%$$

If the value of the percentage of feasibility has been obtained then the next is the appointment of the quality predicate of the product made based on the Rating Scale measurement scale. The scale of the Rating Scale designation is the conversion of qualitative to quantitative data. With the Rating Scale the raw data obtained in the form of numbers is then interpreted in a qualitative sense. The following table is the Rating Scale used to determine the feasibility of the product:

Table 2. Rating Scale

NO	Score in percent (%)	Feasibility Category
1	0 - 25%	very unfit
2	>25% - 27%	not feasible
3	>50% - 75%	Worthy
4	>75% - 100%	Very decent

The results of our research questionnaire are as follows figure 3.

Figure 3. Usability Test Result

Based on the diagram above, the efficiency indicator has a percentage of 82.86% or included in the very feasible category. Meanwhile, for the display has a percentage of 84% or belongs to a very decent category. Then, for interactivity has a percentage of 78.86% or belongs to a very feasible category. The average of the three indicators is 81.9% or it can be said that the usability level of this application is very decent.

5. Conclusion

Based on the research, it can be concluded that, based on the validity test of the Andalus application media experts, the structure and navigation must be improved to be more systematic and consistent. Meanwhile, evaluations from material experts, namely the content delivered must use language that is easily understood by ordinary people. The Andalus application has a very reasonable usability level. The conclusion was taken from the three indicators, namely efficiency, appearance and interactivity, with values of 82.86%, 84%, 78.86%, while for the average value of the three indicators, 81.9%. The results of this study show a high appreciation because the millennials consider the translation of the Qur'an more easily understood and easy to remember. In addition, this application also contains all the verses of the Qur'an so that the millennial more understand the contents of the Qur'an universally.

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